

Results and Discussion

The addition of nitrate to iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium will oxidise iron(II) to iron(III). The quantitative nature of the reaction between nitrate and iron(II) was studied by Krishnamurty⁸ *et al.* The iron(III) produced is in proportion with the nitrate reduced. Basing on this, the iron(III)-thiocyanate complex is developed and the colour of the complex, which is in proportion with the nitrate concentration is measured spectrophotometrically.

In potentiometric and visual methods the passage of carbon dioxide is carried throughout the titration to avoid the aerial oxidation of iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium.

As the titration medium 9-12.5M phosphoric acid is suggested with an optimum concentration of 11 M. Below the concentration of 9 M the colour change of the indicator is sluggish and low values are obtained.

In the particular sample of NPK fertiliser taken there is the presence of only ammonium ion but no other metal ions or nitrate are present to estimable limits. The simplest and most widely used method for the elimination of the effect of ammonium ions is ignition (350°-450°), which causes ammonium salts to sublime or decompose. At these temperatures potassium salts are practically non-volatile⁹. Ammonium nitrate is the most readily decomposed of all the ammonium salts and therefore it is eliminated automatically during the treatment of ignition with nitric acid.

In the case of mureite of potash (fertiliser) sample neither the ammonium nor calcium nor nitrate ions are present in the sample taken. However, there is a possibility of having calcium ions in certain cases which can be eliminated by adding oxalic acid.

If the sample of fertiliser contains nitrate also, it can be estimated directly with the same method without converting the sample to nitrate form and then accounting for the estimation of potassium.

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References

1. H. BECKURTS, *Die Methodin der Massanalyse Vieweg*, Branschweig, 1913.
2. N. A. TERVO and Y. FUNICO, *Bull. Natl. Inst. Agr. Sci.*, Sec. B., 1953, 2, 1.
3. ROLLÉ, WOLFGANG HUEBNER, HEINRICH and HOUTENSTIEN, *Rolf. Chem. Tech. (Berlin)*, 1968, 20, 235.
4. E. KNICHT and E. HIBBERT, *New reduction Methods in volumetric analysis*, 2nd Ed., Longmans., Green., London, 1925.
5. PHLOUZE, *Ann. Chim. et Phys.*, 1847, 20, 129.
6. L. SZEBELLEDY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1928, 73, 145.
7. L. SZEBELLEDY, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1929, 74, 232.
8. N. KRISHNAMURTY, V. SATYANARAYANA and Y. PULLARAO, *Talanta*, 1927, 24, 757.
9. A. MITSCHERLICH, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1861, 460, 485, 89, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1862, 1, 58, 63.

Oscillating Iodine Clock Reaction in Presence of Chloride Ions

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BRIGGS-RAUSCHER Iodine Clock oscillating reaction has been previously studied in aqueous perchloric¹, sulphuric¹, nitric² and phosphoric acid³ media. It has also been reported earlier that the reaction does not take place in hydrochloric acid² medium as the chloride ions act as inhibitors⁴. In the present investigation it has been shown that the reaction is possible in hydrochloric acid medium and in presence of added chloride ions in phosphoric acid medium, provided the chloride ion concentration is not high. A mechanism of chloride inhibition has also been proposed.

Experimental

Three stock solutions were prepared separately and then mixed in equal volumes at room temperature. One was of hydrogen peroxide, another of iodate and phosphoric acid and the third of acetoacetic ester, starch and manganese. Cycling was initiated by adding the solution containing iodate. In order to study the effect of chloride ions, an aqueous sodium chloride solution was prepared and the concentration of chloride ions in the mixture was varied suitably in a systematic manner before initiating the reaction. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred at a more or less fixed slow rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The time period of oscillation was recorded visually from the beautiful appearance or disappearance of blue color.

For studying the reaction in HCl medium, a solution of iodate in hydrochloric acid (in place of phosphoric acid) was prepared and cycling was initiated by adding this solution.

All solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations in the Tables 1 and 2 refer to

TABLE 1—IODINE CLOCK REACTION IN PRESENCE OF CHLORIDE IONS

[Cl ⁻]	Induction period in secs	Color change noted for recording time period	Total time of oscillation	Total No. of oscillations
(I) nil	16	Appearance of blue color	14'8"	52
(II) 0.01(M)	21	—do—	10'2"	25
(III) 0.02(M)	27	—do—	9'1"	24
(IV) 0.03(M)	41	—do—	9'35"	21
(V) 0.04(M)	68	—do—	8'55"	21
(VI) 0.0425(M)	—	No visible Oscillation	—	—

* For correspondence.

TABLE 2—IODINE CLOCK REACTION IN HCl MEDIUM
 $[IO_3^-]=0.067(M)$, $[H_2O_2]=1.127(M)$, $[Acetoacetic\ ester]=0.044(M)$, $[Mn^{++}]=0.0064(M)$, $[starch]=0.019\%$

[HCl]	Induction period in secs	Color change noted for recording time period	Total time of oscillation	Total No. of oscillations	Time reqd. for appearance of permanent starch blue colour
(I) 0.0192(M)	—	Appearance of blue colour	1' 41"	2	Solution remained colourless
(II) 0.026(M)	42	—do—	4' 49"	20	—do—
(III) 0.032(M)	37	—do—	8' 47"	20	10 mins
(IV) 0.0384(M)	31	Disappearance of blue colour	8' 21"	18	9 mins
(V) 0.0472(M)	35	—do—	6' 38"	9	8 mins
(VI) 0.0512(M)	40	—do—	5' 56"	7	7 mins 30 sec
(VII) 0.0576(M)	—	—do—	2' 22"	2	blue colour immediately

concentrations in media. The experimental observations have been summarised in the tables and the plots of time period against time (Figs. 1 and 2) with varying concentrations of chloride ions and hydrochloric acid.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results reveal the following facts :

(1) The induction period increases with increasing chloride ion concentration indicating the inhibiting action of the latter. Such regularity is also observed when the reaction is studied in HCl medium. Some variations in the latter case are probably due to the fact that the concentration of acid must also be sufficiently high for a smooth reaction.

(2) The oscillation period increases with time. Under the present set up it appears that the oscillation periods in the absence and presence of chloride ions are comparable upto a period of about 3 mins. After that period, the time periods for the systems containing chloride ions markedly increase with time. The curves for these systems again run very close (sets II-V in Fig 1). In the case of studying the reaction in HCl medium, however, the curves are quite separate and run upwards in a regular way

with increasing concentration of HCl (sets II-VI in Fig 2).

(3) Total time of oscillation and total no. of oscillations decrease with increasing concentration of chloride ions. In the studies in HCl medium, however, both of these first increase with increasing concentration of HCl and then decrease. This is probably due to the fact that a high concentration of acid also is necessary for good oscillation.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

The role of chloride ions in this reaction may be similar to the role⁵ played by them in Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction⁶ and we propose the following steps. In the first step, chloride successfully competes with both iodide and iodate for the iodous acid

The chlorine species is now further oxidised to HClO₂ which reduces Mn(III) to Mn(II) preventing oscillation.

A lag occurs while Mn(III) is regenerated in step (a)

In step (5), IO_3^- completes the oxidation of the chlorine species to chlorate, which has been found to have no inhibiting action at comparable concentration. Summing these reactions, we get

where (6) = (1) + (2) + (3) + (4) + (5) ... (6)

The reaction is the oxidation of chloride to chlorate by iodate and Mn(III) ions.

Finally, adding to (6), the oxidation of Mn(II) by IO_3^- [equation (a)] and the disproportionation of HIO_2 i.e.,

We get the overall reaction

where (7) = 2(6) + 2(a) + (b)

The mechanism proposed, however, need not be the only one which may account for the effect of chloride ions.

References

1. T. S. BRIGGS and W. C. RAUSCHER, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1978, **50**, 496.
2. B. M. DEV, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1977, **54**, 236.
3. A. K. DUTT and R. S. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 751.
4. D. O. COOKE, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1975, **3**, 377.
5. S. S. JACOBS and IRVING R. EPSTEIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 1721.
6. B. P. BELLOUSOV, *Ref. Radiat. Med.*, 1958 (1958 collection of abstracts on Radiation medicine p. 145, Medgiz, Moscow, 1959).

Quantitative Oxidation of Some Hydrazine Derivatives with Ammonium Hexanitratocerate(IV) as the Oxidant

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HYDRAZINE and its derivatives are quantitatively oxidised with certain organic and inorganic reagents. Barakat and Shaker¹ developed a method for the determination of hydrazines with N-bromosuccinimide in dilute sulphuric acid medium. Iodine monochloride², Fehling's solution³⁻⁵ and ceric sulphate⁶ are the chief inorganic oxidants used for the determination of hydrazine derivatives. Bromate-bromide mixture⁷ in acidic medium has also been employed for the oxidative determination of some hydrazines. Berka and Busev⁸ described an indirect potentiometric method for hydrazine sulphate using Thallium (III) as an oxidant. In the present paper a simple method has been described for the determination of hydrazine

derivatives at the mg level using ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) as the oxidising agent.

Experimental

Hydrazine samples were dissolved in distilled water in a 100 ml volumetric flask to give a concentration of ≈ 1 mg/ml. Ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution (0.15N) A.R., B.D.H. : 8 g was dissolved in 0.5M nitric acid in a 100 ml volumetric flask. Ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (Fe II) (0.025N) A.R., B.D.H. : 2.4508 g was dissolved in distilled water in 250 ml volumetric flask. 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added and the solution made up to the mark with distilled water. Sulphuric acid (1M) : 1M solution of sulphuric acid (v/v) was prepared by dissolving A.R., B.D.H. sample in distilled water. Indicator, 0.001M : Ferroin solution (v/v) in distilled water.

Procedure : An aliquot containing 1-5 mg of the sample was taken in a 100 ml conical flask and 5 ml of 0.15N ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) was added. The flask was stoppered and shaken well. The contents were allowed to react for 10 min at room temperature (25°). After the reaction was over, the stopper was rinsed with 5 ml of distilled water and 10 ml of 1M sulphuric acid was added and the contents shaken for a minute. The unreacted ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate using ferroin indicator. A blank was also run under identical conditions. The recovery of the sample was calculated with the difference in the titre value of the ferrous ammonium sulphate for the sample and the blank.

Results and Discussion

Before applying the method for hydrazine group of compounds, the reaction conditions were developed with hydrazine sulphate. Effect of Ce(IV) concentration, reaction time, reaction temperature and concentration of nitric acid were studied. It was found that 0.15N concentration of Ce(IV) reagent is sufficient for quantitative results. The oxidation of all the compounds could be completed within 10 minutes except semicarbazide and 2-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone which require 20 minutes. The method is applicable even for the higher sample size without loss of accuracy and reproducibility.

The presence of sulphuric acid helps in detecting sharp and distinct end points. The stoichiometry of the reaction was established for every compound by reacting 1-5 mg of the sample for different intervals of reaction time at room temperature with a calculated excess of Ce(IV) reagent. The reaction was carried out at 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 min and the recovery of the sample was calculated. It was found that the consumption of Ce(IV) goes on increasing with increase in reaction time and attain a constant value at 20 minutes. In this way it was found that the consumption of Ce(IV) for phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, semicarbazide, hydrazine